

Dataflow: A Survey of Architectures and Execution Models

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Abstract

This technical report provides a comprehensive overview of different Dataflow architectures, including static, dynamic, and hybrid models. It examines the programmability and execution models such as synchronous and asynchronous. With the continued reduction in transistor size, physical constraints limit their operating frequency, resulting in increased silicon density but inefficient in both performance and energy. Moreover, concurrency has become a significant path to increase computational speed. Researchers and practitioners are exploring alternative architectures, including dataflow types, to overcome this bottleneck. These architectures offer unique performance, energy efficiency, and scalability advantages across various domains.

This survey report provides an overview of different Dataflow architectures, including static, dynamic, and hybrid dataflow, and execution models, such as synchronous and asynchronous. It examines the programmability of these architectures, ranging from fully programmable to domain-specific solutions, in fields like embedded systems, multimedia processing, machine learning, cloud computing, edge computing, and more. Additionally, the report discusses how dataflow is being applied in modern computing systems to meet low-power operation requirements and facilitate specialized hardware acceleration.

Furthermore, the report reviews the latest research in processors, reconfigurable accelerators, and heterogeneous systems utilizing dataflow architectures. It highlights the challenges faced by dataflow architectures and the proposed solutions. This report aims to give readers a concise understanding of state-of-the-art dataflow architectures, including their design types, execution models, programmability, and applications. Lastly, it concludes by outlining future research directions and potential areas of exploration in dataflow architectures.

Keywords: dataflow architecture, control-flow, static dataflow, dynamic dataflow, synchronous dataflow (SDF), Kahn process networks, token matching, scheduling, CGRA, FPGA accelerators, heterogeneous computing, report.

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1 Introduction

The dataflow paradigm is a computational model representing a data flow graph through a system as opposed to the traditional control flow paradigm focusing on sequencing instructions. In dataflow architectures, the execution of instructions is determined by data availability, allowing for concurrent and parallel processing of tasks. Dataflow architectures offer several advantages in modern computing systems, including improved performance, energy efficiency, and scalability.

Dataflow architectures are especially significant in modern computing systems due to the increasing demand for high-performance and power-efficient computing in diverse application domains such as embedded systems, multimedia processing, machine learning, cryptography, cloud computing, and edge computing. Dataflow architectures can leverage the parallelism inherent in many computational tasks, allowing for efficient utilization of computing resources and enabling faster processing of large datasets.

Furthermore, dataflow architectures can be tailored to specific application domains, allowing for specialized and domain-specific optimizations. They are designed to handle different data types, such as streaming, graph, or image data, providing flexibility and adaptability to various computing workloads. Moreover, dataflow architectures can be implemented on specialized hardware accelerators, such as ASICs or FPGAs, to achieve even higher performance and energy efficiency levels in specific domains.

Overall, the dataflow is one of the paradigms to realize and exploit parallelism in modern computing systems, as shown in figure 4, which can be optimized for specific application domains, and offer superior performance and energy efficiency, making them a promising direction for future advancements in computer architecture and computing paradigms.

Unlike the control flow paradigm that compiles to machine code, dataflow compilation goes down to the level of wires, gates, and transistors, resulting in significant acceleration and improved performance. However, adopting the dataflow paradigm requires a different programming approach and often necessitates architecture redesign for specific problems.

The migration of loop execution from software to hardware is a crucial aspect of the dataflow paradigm. This allows

for execution below the machine code level, potentially reducing loop execution time to almost zero, depending on the reusability of data within the migrated loops. Research indicates that dataflow offers advantages over control flow, including speed, power dissipation, and size.

To achieve the benefits mentioned above, some conditions must be met. Firstly, Amdahl's law comes into play, dividing the application into a serial and a parallel part. For substantial acceleration, the parallel part, consisting of loops migrated to the dataflow accelerator, should consume over 95% of the execution time. In contrast, the serial part runs on the control flow paradigm, occupying less than 5% of the application's execution time. Lastly, the level of data reusability within the migrated loops plays a critical role. Higher data reusability leads to better acceleration, as streaming data into a dataflow accelerator can be time-consuming and may only be advantageous with good reusability. Only when the level of data reusability is high can it outweigh the negative impact of slow interconnection buses.

The concept of control flow can be categorized into multi-core and many-core architectures, while the Dataflow concept can be classified into coarse grain and fine grain. In control flow, a key challenge is ensuring that the application software has sufficient parallelism to keep all cores occupied and that partial results are periodically generated in either small (multi-core) or large (many-core) chunks. On the other hand, in Dataflow, the primary concern is the delay until the first partial result is obtained, either at the module level (coarse grain) or the loop iteration level (fine grain). Regarding clock speed, it is common for control flow to have a faster clock, while Dataflow operates at a slower clock speed[57], leading to differences in power requirements between the two approaches.

The Dataflow paradigm achieves high speed due to its compilation to levels significantly below the machine code level. It compiles down to RTL (register transfer level), GTL (gate transfer level), and TTL (transistor transfer level), as shown[57] in Figure 1. Additionally, Dataflow avoids the continuous movement of data through the memory hierarchy, which is typical in control flow-based processors. Another factor is that the Dataflow paradigm employs bit-serial arithmetic and internal arithmetic pipelines, enabling more computational tasks to be completed within a given time frame.

What contributes to the notable power efficiency of the DataFlow paradigm? The operational frequency influences the amount of power consumed. In modern multi-core control flow architectures, frequencies can reach roughly 4 GHz, as in Intel processors. For many-core control flow implementations, frequencies are somewhat lower but still comparatively high. Conversely, FPGA-based DataFlow implementations operate at much lower frequencies, around 200 MHz, as

Figure 1. DataFlow paradigm compiles to lower hardware levels.

exemplified. By dividing 4 GHz by 200 MHz, the power savings ratio of 20. This ratio highlights the significant power efficiency advantage offered by the DataFlow paradigm.

Lastly, why does a DataFlow implementation have a significantly smaller size? The reason is the fundamental differences between the control flow and DataFlow paradigms. Control flow is based on the von Neumann architecture, where only approximately 5% of the chip area is allocated to the Arithmetic Logic Unit (ALU), with the majority of the space utilized for nonfunctional silicon components like caches, branch predictors, and out-of-order execution units. In contrast, the DataFlow paradigm is best implemented on FPGA architectures, where more than 95% of the chip area is dedicated to ALU-type functionalities. The ratio of "more than 95%" to "about 5%" is shown [57] in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Chips of smaller size characterize the data flow paradigm.

Maintaining the 20:1 size ratio even after packaging the chips requires small coolers and fans. Consequently, DataFlow implementations tend to be noisy. The noise arises from two factors: (a) smaller fans inherently produce more noise, and (b) due to the reduced size of the coolers, the fans must rotate at higher speeds to maintain proper cooling, and fast fan rotation constitutes the second significant source of fan noise.

Figure 3. The spectrum of computational architectures, illustrating the trade-off between programmability (Von Neumann) and hardware efficiency (Dataflow).

1.1 THE ARCHITECTURE OF DATAFLOW MACHINES

1.1.1 A Processing Element. A typical dataflow machine comprises multiple processing elements that can communicate with each other. Each processing element has a node template that holds the node’s description and space for input tokens. The node description includes the operand code, which represents the mapping from input to output values, and a list of destination addresses for outgoing arcs. The movement of a token between nodes can be seen as the progression of an activity locus. Nodes that produce more tokens than they consume increase concurrent activities, while nodes consuming multiple tokens require coordination between concurrent activities[77].

In dataflow machines, coordination involves managing the enabling rule for nodes that require multiple inputs. This coordination is handled by the enabling unit, which sequentially accepts tokens, stores them in memory, and checks if a node becomes enabled when all its input ports contain tokens. If a node is enabled, its input tokens are retrieved from memory and a copy of the node, forming an executable packet. This packet includes the input token values, the operand code, and a list of destination addresses. The functional unit processes the packet, computes output values, and combines them with the destination addresses to generate tokens. These tokens are then sent back to the enabling unit, where they may enable other nodes. This concurrent operation of the enabling and functional stages forms a circular pipeline[77].

1.1.2 Dataflow Multiprocessors. While various descriptions of dataflow machines can be found in the literature, most designs can be categorized into one of three structures [77]:

- **One-level dataflow machine:** In this type of machine, such as the one proposed by Arvind and Kathail [4], pipeline concurrency exists within a single processing element. Instructions are executed within the processing element, and the resulting tokens are either used within the same element or transmitted to other processing elements. In certain machines, specific processing elements may be substituted with structure units responsible for storing and manipulating data structures at a lower level.

- **Two-level machine:** In this structure, exemplified by the work of Gurd et al. [37], each functional unit comprises multiple functional elements that concurrently process executable packets. Scheduling is straightforward: An idle functional element is assigned an executable packet. By adjusting the number of functional elements, the power of the functional unit can be aligned with the overall processing element.
- **Two-stage machine:** As described by Dennis and Misunas [20], this type of machine divides the processing elements into two stages. An additional communication medium exists between the stages to transmit executable packets to the functional elements. The two-stage structure is advantageous when the functional stage is heterogeneous, meaning that certain functional elements possess specialized capabilities.

1.1.3 Communication. In an actual dataflow machine, the communication medium can take various forms, such as a tree, a ring, a binary n-cube, or an equidistant $n \times n$ switch. Another important aspect is the type of connections provided by the communication medium. Dataflow machines can have either a direct or packet communication architecture, similar to circuit switching and packet switching networks in traditional computing[77].

In a direct communication architecture, adjacent nodes in the dataflow graph are assigned to the same processing element or processing elements with direct connections. One key characteristic of this architecture is that the communication medium delivers tokens in the same order they were received. If queues are incorporated into the communication medium, it becomes possible to execute unsafe graphs and dataflow graphs where arcs can contain multiple tokens without compromising determinacy.

On the other hand, packet communication allows for more excellent load distribution and parallelism in the communication unit. It can be implemented using asynchronously operating packet-switching modules, which offer parallelism and redundancy. These modules accept tokens and forward them to other modules based on their destination addresses. However, packet communication requires safeguards to prevent deadlock, as contention can block essential paths. Machines with redundant communication paths may not maintain the order of packets, and determinate execution can only be ensured for safe graphs where the order of tokens is preserved. The communication unit’s optimal structure and performance limitations are subjects of debate among dataflow architects.

There are different perspectives among architects regarding the design of dataflow machines. Some advocate for a large number of slow and simple processing elements connected to a high-bandwidth communication unit, which is suitable for a one-level machine structure. Others argue that significant bottlenecks occur in the communication unit as

processing elements increase. They focus on building powerful processing elements and often postpone the design of the higher-level structure. Sometimes, a single processing element is presented as a complete machine[36].

1.1.4 Data Structures. In a dataflow graph, values are passed between nodes without being stored in memory at that level of abstraction. A copy of the value is sent to each node if multiple nodes require a value. This also applies to data structures, which are treated as values in the dataflow graph. In a tagged-token machine with a limited token size, a complete structure can be sent to a node by packaging each element as a separate token with subsequent tags to distinguish them. For example, a retrieve operation consumes a complete structure and an index and produces a copy of the retrieved element[77].

However, implementing structure copying directly is only sometimes practical for large data structures, as it would significantly burden the machine. To address this, many dataflow machines include a facility to store structures. In these machines, elements can be retrieved by sending requests to the unit where the structure is stored. Updating a structure in the dataflow graph, similar to a selective update operation, involves consuming the old structure, the index, and the new value and producing a completely new structure. Even when structures are stored, copying is still necessary for this process.

Several approaches are employed to reduce excessive structure copying. Structures that are not shared do not need to be copied before an update, and a reference count mechanism can be used to detect such cases. This mechanism is also helpful for garbage collection. For shared structures, copying can be minimized by storing the structure as a tree and copying only the updated node and its ancestors. Another approach involves providing restrictive access primitives in the programming language, leading to the concept of streams. Streams are structures that can only be produced and consumed sequentially, allowing for more efficient processing in some machines and increasing effective parallelism.

Non-strict treatment of structures is another technique that increases parallelism. It allows access to elements before the entire structure has been fully created. Arvind and Thomas[7] introduced this concept, I-structures (incomplete structures), which require specialized hardware to defer fetches of elements that are not yet available.

Various proposed solutions have been proposed to handle structures, but a universal solution is complex and elusive. Gaudiot [28] suggests two approaches to avoid storing: defining medium-grain structure operations and defining tag manipulation instructions that exploit the frequent interaction between array indexing, iteration, or recursion. First proposed by Bowen [9] and extensively used in Manchester [78], tag manipulation is limited to algorithms where data structures are consumed entirely. Simulation studies

have shown that tag manipulation performs better than I-structures in specific algorithms[29].

Figure 4. Some of the design options for parallel computers

2 Evolution and Classification of Dataflow Architectures

During the 1970s and early 1980s, computer architecture research focused heavily on hardware architectures for data-flow. Utilizing data-flow graphs for parallel computations was initially introduced in the late 1960s [43]. The first operational data-flow computation system debuted in 1977 [15] at the University of Utah. Jack Dennis of MIT proposed the first static data-flow machine [20]. It was a special-purpose machine designed for the efficient execution of a class of signal-processing applications. Despite their significant shortcomings and design problems, these machines served as the basis for many current dataflow projects.

The abstract dataflow model uses tokens to carry data values as they travel along the arcs connecting different program graph instructions. These arcs are assumed to be first-in-first-out (FIFO) queues with unbounded storage capacity. However, implementing this model directly is not feasible. Instead, the dataflow execution model is generally categorized as static or dynamic [45]. This has been discussed in detail in the Programmability section.

Static data-flow architectures are commonly used in digital signal processing, multimedia processing, and image processing applications. The data processing tasks are well-defined and do not change significantly during run-time. These applications can benefit from the predictability and efficiency of static data-flow architectures. The first dynamic data-flow machine was the MIT Tagged-Token Data-flow Architecture [35]. The architecture used a token-based approach to implement a dynamic data-flow graph, with each token representing a data value or a control signal. Dynamic data-flow architectures are used extensively in stream processing applications, where data is continuously generated and processed in real-time. These architectures can handle the variability and unpredictability of data streams, making them well-suited for sensor data processing and real-time analytics.

Milad[56] describe a hybrid processor that combines multiple computing architectures, including multicore processors, manycore graphical processors, and data-flow processors on a single chip die for high-performance computing. This form of hybrid architecture attempt to balance the benefits of static and dynamic approaches by combining them. They provide a fixed data-flow graph at design time but allow limited runtime modifications to the graph to adapt to changing workload requirements. This approach can provide better performance predictability and optimization opportunities while maintaining flexibility.

The demand for faster and more energy-efficient architectures is increasing in modern data-intensive workloads. Depending on the nature of the application and the need for run-time changes, these lead to adopting different types of data-flow architecture. One such dynamic data-flow is Reconfigurable Data-flow Accelerators (RDAs) to exploit data-flow parallelism and scalability like SARA[86] - a novel mapping strategy to spatially map a program onto distributed resources of an RDA, NeuFlow[26]- scalable dataflow hardware architecture optimized for vision algorithms, Aurochs [79]- a threading model for vector data-flow accelerators that extracts massive parallelism from irregular data structures, using lightweight thread contexts. RDA solution for accelerating AI for science workloads, with observed efficacy in diverse science applications[22].

One more dynamic data-flow architecture with natural coarse-grained implementation is Coarse-grained reconfigurable architecture. CGRAs possess near-ASIC energy efficiency and performance with post-fabrication software like programmability[52]. It helps in improving the efficiency of general-purpose processing as energy becomes a key constraint, reducing the demand for specialized hardware for most applications, as shown in work [32]. Similarly, Fine-grained dataflow architectures offer advantages over traditional von Neumann architectures for efficiently processing algorithms like CNNs [85]. This is because they operate more parallel and distributed, allowing for faster execution and lower power usage. Additionally, these architectures can be programmed to perform various tasks beyond CNNs, making them versatile and adaptable.

Actors: The application graph consists of nodes, which are called actors (computation tasks represented by a circle) that are interconnected by edges (arcs), as described in section 5.

Scheduling consists of three operations:

- assigning actors to processors(assignment)
- determining the order of execution of the actors on each processor(ordering)
- determining the exact starting time of each actor(timing)

Every system that executes a dataflow graph must perform all of these tasks; however, depending on the implementation and the information about the execution requirements of the

graph, some functions may be performed at “compile time,” leaving others to be performed at “run time”. Lee and Ha [47] propose a scheduling taxonomy based on which scheduling tasks are performed at compile time and which at run-time; defining four scheduling classes as shown in figure 5, we use the same terminology here.

	Assignment	Ordering	Timing
Fully Dynamic	RUN-TIME	RUN-TIME	RUN-TIME
Static Assignment	COMPILE-TIME	RUN-TIME	RUN-TIME
Self-Timed	COMPILE-TIME	COMPILE-TIME	RUN-TIME
Fully Static	COMPILE-TIME	COMPILE-TIME	COMPILE-TIME

Figure 5. The time which the scheduling activities “assignment”, “ordering”, and “timing” are performed is shown for four classes of schedulers. The scheduling activities are listed on top and the strategies on the left [47].

To reduce run-time computation costs, performing as many of the three scheduling tasks as possible at compile time is advantageous, especially in the context of algorithms with hard real-time constraints. However, dynamic scheduling is more practical because compilers do not tend to have the sophistication to schedule a complex operation before run-time.

In [47], a *fully-static* strategy is a scheduling approach that performs all scheduling tasks at compile time. Relaxing this approach, where the compiler determines both the processor assignment and the order of execution of each node but does not determine the exact timing of actor execution, where inter-processor communication exists, implicit or explicit synchronization operations are required so that actors will wait for data to become available, this gives rise to the *self-timed* strategy. This technique is commonly used when there is no hardware support for scheduling, such as when generating code for networks of von Neumann processors with shared memory. One such machine is the Gabriel system [48]. *Static assignment* scheduling is a strategy that performs only the assignment step at compile time; for example, It is also possible to partition the actors of the dataflow graph between the various processors in advance but then have the processors determine the order of actor execution at run time. Many dataflow machines work this way, for example, the Monsoon architecture [63]. Finally, a *fully dynamic* scheduling strategy is deemed an approach that makes all scheduling decisions at run-time. As we move towards a fully dynamic strategy, the run-time overhead increases; however, the more run-time decisions we make, the more generally applicable the scheduling strategy becomes. Static techniques depend on how much compile-time information is available about the application; this makes them applicable to a narrower application domain.

A *quasi-static* scheduling technique tackles data-dependent execution by localizing run-time decision-making to specific types of data-dependent constructs, such as conditionals and data-dependent iterations. An *ordered transactions* strategy is a self-timed approach where the order in which processors communicate is determined at compile time, and the target hardware enforces the predetermined transaction order during run-time. Such a strategy leads to a low-overhead inter-processor communication mechanism.

The trade-off between the generality of the applications that a particular scheduling model can target, and the run-time overhead and implementation complexity entailed by that model as shown in figure 6

Figure 6. Trade-off of generality against run-time overhead and implementation complexity .

Suppose we accurately understand how each actor executes, the dependencies between data elements, and knowledge about the target architecture’s characteristics and communication limitations between processors. In that case, creating an optimal schedule for executing a dataflow graph on a parallel processor system is possible without incurring any scheduling-related runtime overhead. However, in practical scenarios, the problem of scheduling tasks across multiple processors is NP-complete, even in more superficial cases. This means that finding the optimal solution becomes computationally challenging. As a result, many researchers employ heuristic approaches to obtain schedules close to optimal, using different criteria to define what is considered "good" regarding schedule quality. For a more detailed examination of the complexity of multiprocessor scheduling and its NP-completeness, please refer to the discussion in [72].

Even in cases where it is feasible to generate a fully static schedule, there are instances where it is preferable to generate code for a self-timed system. This preference arises because a self-timed system offers greater resilience to variations in timing caused by minor differences in clock rates, errors in timing specifications, interrupts, and other factors. As long as the generated code adheres to Kahn’s model of

communicating sequential processes [30], the self-timed system will execute reliably, irrespective of timing variations.

When the dataflow graph includes dynamic actors with execution dependencies based on data, it becomes evident that some scheduling decisions must be made during runtime. However, many of the techniques employed for compile-time scheduling can be adapted to remain applicable to dynamic dataflow graphs. Thus, there is no necessity to transition to a completely dynamic execution model.

Modifying the granularity of the Data Flow Graph (DFG) to match a heterogeneous multicore platform using Quasi-Static Schedules (QSSs) offers the potential for improved performance by reducing dynamic scheduling overhead and facilitating optimizations for groups of actors rather than individual actors in isolation. However, existing approaches in the literature for computing QSSs assume DFGs with unbounded First In First Out (FIFO) channels. In practice, DFGs mapped to multi-core platforms need to adhere to FIFO channels with limited capacities.

Joachim [25] proposes a novel algorithm for adjusting the capacity of FIFO channels to address this limitation. This algorithm enables the application of QSSs to DFGs with limited channel capacities, thereby extending the applicability of QSS refinements to general multi-core targets. With this advancement, the benefits of QSSs can now be leveraged in scenarios where DFGs are mapped to multi-core platforms with limited channel capacities.

2.1 Synergizing Dataflow with Control-Flow: Combining Paradigms for Improved Performance

Pure dataflow computers based on the single-token-per-arc or tagged-token dataflow models often have poor performance when executing sequential code. The limitation stems from the requirement that instructions from the same thread can only be issued to the dataflow pipeline once their preceding instructions have been completed. In an 8-stage dataflow pipeline, instructions from the same thread can be issued at most every eight cycles, resulting in low utilization of the dataflow processor under low load conditions. An additional drawback relates to the overhead associated with token matching. Prior to executing a dyadic instruction, two result tokens must be present, causing a bubble in the execution stage(s) of the dataflow processor pipeline. These disruptions, known as pipeline bubbles, can impact system performance as they accumulate. In fine-grain dataflow, a context switch occurs after every instruction execution, preventing the optimization of data access time through register usage. This also avoids pipeline bubbles caused by dyadic instructions and reduces the overall number of tokens during program execution. To address these issues, a potential solution involves integrating dataflow with control-flow mechanisms. Research projects have explored the symbiosis

between dataflow and von Neumann architectures by developing von Neumann/dataflow, a hybrid systems. These hybrids range from simple extensions of von Neumann processors with additional instructions to specialized dataflow systems that aim to reduce overhead by increasing the execution grain size and employing various scheduling, allocation, and resource management techniques used in von Neumann computers. These developments demonstrate that dataflow and von Neumann architectures are not entirely separate worlds but rather represent two ends of a spectrum of possible computer systems.

Various approaches have been developed to integrate control-flow and dataflow, including [8] but not limited to:

- hybrid dataflow,
- threaded dataflow,
- large-grain dataflow,
- dataflow with complex machine operations,
- RISC dataflow.

2.1.1 Hybrid Dataflow: Initial efforts to combine dataflow computing with other paradigms were explored during the early 1980s, taking various approaches. Most existing hybrid architectures incorporate dataflow elements in the Von Neumann computing model. The property of hybrid dataflow is used to design an Instruction Set Architecture (ISA) extension for the RISC-V architecture capable of executing explicit dataflow instructions and added the dataflow sub-ISA to the RISC-V ISA and simulated using the gem5 simulator[13]. Its heterogeneous hybrid architecture runs applications using dataflow and out-of-order execution models and shows an improvement in performance. The data flow and control processing optimizations provide performance gains comparable to custom ASICs for a broad range of vision benchmarks [12]. Hybrid architecture – a kind that fuses systolic fabrics for efficiency and dataflow fabrics for flexible parallelism to have superior digital signal processor[82].

There is no unanimous agreement regarding hardware architectures on the optimal approach for achieving a hybrid system. Different strategies exist, ranging from von Neumann architectures with additional dataflow elements to dataflow architectures with incorporated von Neumann components. Several examples of such hybrid architectures can be found in the work of Iannucci [41]; Nikhil and Arvind [61]; Papadopoulos and Traub [65]

Reconfigurable dataflow hardware requires reconfiguration of the hardware every time a new program needs to be executed, resulting in reduced efficiency. To address these, hybrid architecture was considered [27], where a greedy algorithm is used for scheduling programs on dataflow and control flow processors to improve execution efficiency. Hybrid dataflow helps in realizing the hierarchical organization of a distributed, parallel and heterogeneous computer system[21]. This architecture makes use of implicit parallel execution of code approaches based on dataflow analysis at

the instruction level. Figure 7 shows a simplified version of this. Similar work at processor level [81], DiAG- a dataflow architecture that can fetch, decode, and execute instructions normally but, as it executes, also constructs a hardware datapath that replicates the program’s dataflow graph.

2.1.2 (Multi-) Threaded Dataflow: Threaded dataflow refers to a modified approach of the dataflow principle where instructions belonging to specific instruction streams are processed sequentially in consecutive machine cycles. In this technique, subgraphs within a dataflow graph that have limited parallelism are identified and transformed into sequential threads. The matching unit in the system issues these threads of instructions one after another without matching additional tokens except for the first instruction in each thread. Threaded dataflow encompasses various techniques employed in processors like Epsilon-1[34], Epsilon-2 [33], EM-4[71] (with strongly connected arcs), and Monsoon[64] (with direct token recycling). Unlike traditional dataflow, instructions within a thread share data through registers instead of writing it back to memory. This approach improves the performance of single-thread execution and reduces the overall number of tokens required for scheduling instructions, resulting in savings in hardware resources. Furthermore, pipeline bubbles caused by dyadic instructions within a thread are eliminated. Efficient synchronization mechanisms play a crucial role in threaded dataflow machines, and one common approach is *direct matching*, which does not require associative mechanisms. Implementing an effective synchronization mechanism is a key design challenge in threaded dataflow architectures [70].

2.1.3 Large-Grain Dataflow: The *coarse-grain* (or large-grain) dataflow model is another technique that combines dataflow and control-flow. In this model, macro dataflow actors are activated following the dataflow paradigm, while instruction sequences represented by actors are executed in a von Neumann style. Large-grain dataflow machines employ FIFO buffers to decouple the matching stage (signal or synchronization stage) from the execution stage. This decoupling helps avoid pipeline bubbles, improving overall efficiency. By separating the matching and execution stages, large-grain dataflow machines can utilize off-the-shelf microprocessors to support the execution stage. This approach allows for the integration of traditional microprocessors into the dataflow architecture. Many recent dataflow architectures adopt this coarse-grain model as it offers flexibility and compatibility with existing microprocessors.

2.1.4 Dataflow with Complex Machine Operations. Another approach to minimize the overhead of instruction-level synchronization is using complex machine instructions, such as vector instructions. These instructions can be implemented using pipeline techniques, similar to vector computers. Rather than accessing structured data element by

element from a structure store, these instructions enable referencing structured data in blocks and can be supplied in burst mode. This deviates from the I-structure scheme, where each data element within a complex data structure is fetched individually from a structure store. Complex machine operations also enable the exploitation of parallelism at the sub-instruction level, allowing the machine to partition a complex operation into suboperations that can be executed simultaneously. This can eliminate the need for multiple nested loops. By using FIFO buffers, the machine can decouple the firing stage (where instructions are matched) from the execution stage, bridging the different execution times required for processing a mixed stream of simple and complex instructions.

Unlike conventional dataflow architectures, in this approach, tokens do not carry data except for boolean values (true or false). Instead, data is moved and transformed within the execution stage. This technique is employed in architectures such as the Decoupled Graph/Computation Architecture[24], the Stollmann Dataflow Machine [62], and the ASTOR architecture [76]. These architectures combine complex machine instructions with the large-grain dataflow model described earlier.

In the SIGMA-1 architecture, the structure-flow technique [39] further enhances fine-grain dataflow computers by introducing structure load/store instructions. These instructions facilitate the movement of entire vectors or other structured data to and from a structure store. Arithmetic operations are executed by the cyclic pipeline within a processing element (PE).

2.1.5 RISC dataflow. The emergence of RISC dataflow architectures provided momentum for developing dataflow/Von Neumann hybrids. These architectures aimed to execute existing software designed for traditional processors. Utilizing such machines as a bridge between conventional systems and new dataflow supercomputers, the transition from imperative Von Neumann languages to dataflow languages was intended to be smoother for programmers. The fundamental principles guiding the development of the RISC dataflow architecture can be summarized as follows:

- Utilize a RISC-like instruction set.
- Modify the architecture to support multi-threaded computation.
- Introduce fork and join instructions for managing multiple threads.
- Implement all global storage as I-structure storage.
- Incorporate load/store instructions that execute in split-phase mode.

The Parallel RISC (p-RISC) architecture, developed at MIT by Nikhil and Arvind[61], is a realization of the abovementioned principles. It comprises processing elements (PEs)

with their local memory and global memory. These components are interconnected using a communication network based on packet switching.

3 Execution model

Data-driven computation has been around since the early days of electronic computing. Asynchronous in/out channels, introduced in the 1950s, were some of the first implementations of data-driven execution. With the development of multi-programmed operating systems in the 1960s, large-scale asynchronous parallelism became a reality.

In areas where algorithms are highly dependent on input data, and scheduling must be done at runtime, asynchronous machines are necessary. While computations in asynchronous machines are free to follow their instruction streams, they must be synchronized at the points where interaction occurs. This synchronization overhead is the price to be paid for the higher utilization allowed by the asynchronous operation.

Dataflow machines are a type of fine-grain parallel computer that minimize synchronization overhead by providing special hardware and coding programs in a unique format. In dataflow machines, scheduling is based on the availability of data, which is called data-driven execution. This coordination scheme uses the arrival of a data item to enable the execution of an instruction, eliminating the need for separate control flow arcs. Dataflow machines can improve scalability and make segmentation trivial by dividing the program into many small processes[77].

Dataflow architectures represent a radical alternative to von Neumann architectures because they use dataflow graphs as their machine language. Dataflow graphs, as opposed to conventional machine languages, specify only a partial order on the execution of instructions and thus provide opportunities for parallel and pipelined execution at the level of individual instructions. For example, the dataflow graph for the expression,

$$(a * b) + (c * d)$$

It only specifies that both multiplications be executed before the addition. The multiplications can be executed in any order, even in parallel. The advantage of this flexibility becomes apparent when considering that the order in which a,b,c, and d become available may not be known at compile time. For example, computations for operands a and b may take longer than computations for c and d [41].

The existing dataflow computers have predominantly relied on asynchronous operating structures, with many researchers considering asynchronism as a fundamental aspect of dataflow computations. However, dataflow computations do not necessarily have to be asynchronous. Liu [51] proposes a model of dataflow computations based on dataflow program graphs. In this model, synchronous can be achieved

by separating the triggering signals from the tokens and expressing them with an explicit direct control signal C instead of implicit triggering signals.

The granularity of the system determines the degree of parallelism in the dataflow. Figure 7 indicates that neither fine-grained (as in traditional dataflow) nor coarse-grained (as in sequential execution) dataflow offers the best parallel performance. Still, rather a medium-grained approach should be used. This suggests that some form of hybrid—dataflow with von Neumann extensions, or vice versa— would offer the best performance.

Figure 7. Dataflow granularity optimization curve, (based on Sterling et al. [74]).

In the past few decades, there have been significant developments in various data-flow Models of Computation (MoCs). These MoCs are typically categorized based on their level of expressiveness, which determines the types of applications that can be modeled using a given data-flow MoC. It can be observed that the analyzability of data-flow MoCs is inversely coupled to their expressiveness, i.e., some problems are decidable for less expressive data-flow MoCs, but are not decidable for more expressive ones (refer to Figure 8). In the early design stages of an embedded system, the analyzability of properties such as required channel bandwidth, deadlock freedom, and schedulability is of utmost importance. Therefore, data-flow MoCs with higher analyzability are generally preferred. For instance, scheduling actors on computational resources at compile time (static scheduling) is usually favored over runtime scheduling (dynamic scheduling) to minimize the overhead associated with the scheduling strategy[38]. However, it is crucial to note that static schedules can only be generated for data-flow MoCs with limited expressiveness. This limitation is discussed further below.

3.1 Static dataflow:

The static dataflow model illustrated in Figure 9 allows the execution of an operator in the form of a node only when there are tokens (values) in all input edges, and no token is present in the output [45]. This model can exploit structural parallelism and pipelined parallelism, and it is commonly

Figure 8. Illustrated above is a hierarchy [75] of diverse data-flow MoCs. The hierarchy is partitioned into static (light blue) data-flow MoCs and dynamic (light red) data-flow MoCs. The three static data-flow MoCs Homogeneous (Synchronous) Data Flow (HSDF), Synchronous Data Flow (SDF), and Cyclo-Static Data Flow (CSDF). And the dynamic data-flow MoCs Boolean Data Flow (BDF), Dennis Data Flow (DDF), Kahn Process Networks (KPNs), and Non-Determinate Data Flow (NDF) [38].

used in applications that involve frequent numeric computing structures.

Figure 9. Basic Organization of the Static Dataflow Model

3.1.1 Synchronous Dataflow. Synchronous dataflow (SDF) is a subclass of dataflow graphs that lack data dependency and consist only of synchronous actors. SDF graphs have several properties that make them suitable for static scheduling [49] [50]:

- The number of firings for each actor in an SDF graph can be determined at compile time, allowing for the construction of a deterministic acyclic precedence graph and optimal or near-optimal schedules if the execution time of each actor is known.
- Memory requirements can be verified at compile time for nonterminating programs in SDF graphs. Deadlock conditions can be analytically determined for any SDF graph, helping to identify unintended halts in program execution.
- The maximum execution speed of an SDF graph can be determined at compile time-based on the known execution times of each actor. For terminating programs, this corresponds to finding the minimum makespan, while for nonterminating programs, it means finding the minimum period of a periodic schedule.

- In nonterminating SDF graphs executing according to a periodic schedule, data can be statically buffered between actors without needing FIFO queues or dynamically allocated memory. The compiler can associate memory locations with actor firings, serving as repositories for input and output data.
- Static scheduling in SDF offers cost-effective architectures but comes with increased compile-time complexity. However, not all applications can be statically scheduled. Despite not allowing data-dependent firing of actors, SDF still supports specific control structures such as recurrences, manifest iteration, and conditional assignment.

Synchronous Dataflow [46] can be characterized by the following features: synchronous activations, support for multiple input/output ports, data pushing (with some limitations), use of immutable data, static behavior, functional nodes performing specific operations, allowance for cycles in the graph, support for compound nodes during design-time, restriction on arc joins and allowance for arc splits. Calculating a schedule should tell if the program will deadlock, the maximum size of every arc, and every node's activation rate.

Synchronous Dataflow is characterized by activated nodes on a fixed, pre-determined, and repeating schedule. Each port on a node sends and receives a fixed number of tokens upon every activation. This approach ensures that the program will experience a smooth transition once a schedule is established. However, the downside is that Synchronous Dataflow is less flexible than asynchronous Dataflow, and not all programs can be effectively defined or expressed in terms of Synchronous Dataflow.

The state of a Synchronous Dataflow program is defined by the number of tokens on every arc. Finding a schedule is called compiling and is analogous to compiling a traditional programming language like C++. The runtime requirements for a Synchronous Dataflow engine are minimal since most of the hard work has already been done. It must have space for and keep track of tokens, contain the node definitions to execute, and have some process to activate the nodes based on the schedule.

Systems with small granularity in dataflow are characterized by nodes that perform simple, primitive operations such as addition. Similar to electronic circuits, these systems often employ synchronous activation due to the higher data transfer rate between nodes compared to systems with large granularity.

3.2 Dynamic dataflow:

As shown in Figure 10, the dynamic dataflow model enables the operator connected to a node to execute when all input edges contain tokens with identical marks. Unlike the static dataflow model, each edge can hold multiple signed tokens removed from the input edges and generate a token

with a corresponding mark on the output when the node is executed[45]. The dynamic dataflow model employs loop and recursive parallelism, which dynamically arise during program execution and require support for connecting operands. Many dynamic dataflow architectures require an associative memory to connect suitable data tokens, but designs such as Monsoon [64], EM-4 [71], and Epsilon-2 [33] favor eliminating associative concatenation of tokens in favor of explicit and direct memory addressing through direct concatenation of operands.

Figure 10. Basic Organization of the Dynamic Dataflow Model

3.3 Restricted data flow:

A performance penalty is associated with using communication arcs in dataflow architectures. In particular, the penalty arises from the need to perform associative searches through the entire program to find the correct tokens to connect. This time-consuming process requires matching hardware to identify the appropriate tokens. As a result, the performance of dataflow architectures can be significantly impacted by the use of communication arcs. Some architectures have adopted more restricted forms of dataflow [14] [41] [61] [64] [65] that minimize the need for associative searches to address this issue. These architectures may use direct memory addressing or other techniques to reduce the overhead of searching for tokens. By doing so, they can achieve better performance and more efficient execution of dataflow programs.

To exploit whatever parallelism exists in the instruction stream, one requires an execution model devoid of artifacts that limit the utilization of that parallelism. The abstract restricted data flow (RDF) paradigm is such a model. It was the first implemented in High Performance Substrate, a new microarchitecture targeted for implementing very high performance computing engines [66] and related several issues where address in [67]. It is characterized by three parameters: window size, issue rate, and instruction class latencies [73]. It was found that more than 17 instructions could be executed per cycle removing all constraints except the program semantics [11]. High-performance machines can be built by taking advantage of some of this parallelism. Removing all constraints is currently impractical. Even removing many constraints is extremely difficult to implement in a

single microprocessor. Not only is the number of execution units too great, but the issue and completion mechanisms have become too difficult to manage. Also, the usage of the execution units will need to be more efficient.

A restricted data flow algorithm is used to take advantage of the natural parallelism that is present in any program. It reduces pipeline stalls by issuing instructions in order, executing them out of order, and finally committing them in order. Implementation of a superscalar, speculative execution SPARC-V9 microprocessor incorporating Restricted Data Flow principles as shown in the work of Simone. [73].

4 Hardware implementation

The dataflow architecture has supported specialized hardware design for deep neural and machine learning applications requiring high computation and energy-efficient systems. The Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is a cutting-edge algorithm widely used in various applications like face recognition, intelligent monitoring, image recognition, and text recognition. However, its high computational complexity requires efficient hardware accelerators to leverage parallel processing for CNN. While FPGA and ASIC-based accelerators prioritize performance and power consumption, they often sacrifice generality. On the other hand, more general accelerators like GPUs consume higher power. Fine-grained dataflow architectures provide a promising solution to efficiently process CNN-like algorithms with low power consumption and high computational efficiency without sacrificing generality. Consequently, there have been considerable efforts in implementing and optimizing CNN on fine-grained dataflow architecture-based accelerators.[85]. The dataflow method is scalable and can be used for large data dimensions with limited on-chip memory.

Dataflow at the ISA level:

The instruction execution mechanism of a dataflow processor is fundamentally different from that of a von Neumann processor. Consider the MIT Tagged-Token architecture [5]; rather than using a program counter to determine the next instruction to be executed and then fetching operands accordingly, a dataflow machine provides a low-level synchronization mechanism in the form of a Waiting-Matching store that dispatches only those instructions for which data are already available. This mechanism relies on tagging each datum with the address of the instruction to which it belongs and the context in which the instruction is to be executed [41].

Execution of a data-flow program is data-driven; that is, each instruction is enabled for execution just when the execution of a predecessor instruction has supplied each required operand. These data-flow programs are well suited to representing signal processing computations such as waveform generation, modulation, and filtering, in which a group of operations is to be performed once for each sample (in time)

of the signals being processed. The elementary data-flow processor described in [20], avoids the problems of processor switching and processor/memory interconnection in attempts to adapt conventional Von Neuman-type machines for parallel computation. Sections of the machine communicate by the transmission of fixed-size information packets, and the machine is organized so that the sections can tolerate packet transmission delays without compromising the hardware's effective utilization. The hardware support for data model execution describes in [40].

5 Programmability

A traditional von Neumann processor has fundamental characteristics that reduce its effectiveness in a parallel machine. Its performance suffers from long memory and communication latencies, which are unavoidable in a parallel machine. They do not provide suitable synchronization mechanisms for frequent task switching between parallel activities, again inevitable in a parallel machine. Traditional programming languages are not easily extended to incorporate parallelism. Loss of determinacy adds significant complexity to establishing correctness (this includes debugging). It is a significantly added complication for the programmer to explicitly manage parallelism- to identify and schedule parallel tasks small enough to utilize the machine effectively but large enough to keep resource-management overheads reasonable[5].

Most of the work on architectural concepts for data flow computation is based on a program representation known as data flow program graphs [18], which evolved from the work of Rodriguez[68], Adams[2] and Karp and Miller[42]. Data flow computers are a form of language-based architecture in which program graphs are the base language. Data flow program graphs serve as a formally specified interface between system architecture on one hand and user programming language on the other. The architect's task is to define and realize a computer system that faithfully implements the formal behavior of program graphs; the language implementer's task is to translate source language programs into their equivalent as program graphs.

A program graph in data flow consists of actors linked by arcs. One type of actor is the operator, depicted in Figure 11 as a circle with a function symbol inside (in this example, + for addition).

Figure 11. Data Flow Actor

An operator has input and output arcs that hold tokens with values. The arcs indicate the paths over which values are

Figure 12. Firing Rule: (a) before; (b) after

conveyed from one actor to others. Tokens are placed on and removed from the arcs based on firing rules, exemplified for an operator in Figure 12. Tokens must be present on all input arcs, and no token should exist on any output arc of the actor to enable it. Any enabled actor may be fired. For an operator, one token is removed from each input arc, the specified function is applied to the carried values, and tokens with the result value are placed on the output arcs. As shown in Figure 13, operators may be connected to create program graphs. By providing tokens with values for x and y on the two inputs, the program graph enables the computation of the value $z = (x+y) * (x-y)$, with a token carrying the result value on output arc z . Another representation of data flow programs, more similar to the machine language used in prototype data flow computers, is also helpful in understanding how these machines operate.

Figure 13. Interconnection of operators

Figure 14. Activity template

In this representation, a data flow program is a set of activity templates, with each template corresponding to one or more actors in a program graph. Figure 14 illustrates an activity template corresponding to the plus operator in Figure 12. This template has four fields: an operation code that indicates the operation to be performed, two receivers waiting for operand values, and destination fields (in this case, one) that specify what to do with the operation's result on the operands. This example illustrates two critical properties of the dataflow approach:

- Parallelism, i.e., nodes may execute in parallel unless there is an explicit data dependence between them.
- Determinacy, i.e., results- do not depend on the relative order in which potentially parallel nodes execute.

In this example, a single wave of tokens on the input arcs produces a single wave of tokens on the output arcs. Graphs that have this property are called well-behaved. All acyclic graphs for arithmetic and logical expressions are well-behaved. Unlike the plus operator, two control operators switch and merge are not well-behaved in isolation. But yield well-behaved graphs when used in conditional and loop schemas, as discussed in the work of Arvind [6]. The essential point to remember in implementing the dataflow model is that tokens imply storage. The token storage mechanism is the critical feature of a dataflow architecture. While the dataflow model assumes unbounded FIFO queues on the arcs and FIFO behavior at the nodes, it is challenging to implement this model strictly.

Two alternative approaches are *Static dataflow*: which provides a fixed amount of storage per arc, and *Dynamic or tagged-token dataflow*: which provides dynamic allocation of token storage out of a shared pool and assumes that tokens carry tags to indicate their logical position on the arcs.

Conventional programming models and languages based on barrier and lock paradigms cannot exploit parallelism at the finer grain, losing some opportunities for concurrent execution. This issue becomes more severe as the scale of the machines increases. Nevertheless, its implementations suffered from huge overheads limiting the applicability and, consequently, the model's success [3]. In order to overcome these issues, dataflow is enforced at a coarser granularity.

5.1 Functional Languages And Dataflow

The Von Neumann machine, as a current state machine, operates by modifying its memory content, including registers, during instruction execution. This programming approach is known for its side effects, where changes in state occur as a result of instruction execution. However, the physical separation of memory and processing units in the Von Neumann scheme leads to a bottleneck due to constant data transfer. Alternative approaches, such as functional programming and data flow machines [31], are being explored to address

these limitations, as they offer potential solutions to these drawbacks.

5.2 Data-flow Programming

In traditional imperative programming, programmers control when and how instructions are executed. However, in data-flow programming, programmers only need to define the data dependencies between instructions. The instructions are then scheduled or fired by the underlying data-flow architecture [20] [83]. This allows for concurrent execution on processing units (PEs) if enough is available. In addition to exploring architectures that support parallel executions, researchers have also focused on compiling conventional imperative languages into data-flow hardware.

The data-flow model offers two types of parallelism [6]. First, nodes can be executed in parallel if the required data is available. In models where arcs can hold only one token at most, nodes without data dependencies can be fired concurrently. In models where arcs can hold multiple tokens, nodes with data dependencies can also be fired concurrently if fire rules are satisfied. The second type of parallelism arises from different waves of the graph. Once the dependent data becomes available, nodes can be fired even from the same node. A mechanism to distinguish nodes from different waves is necessary to exploit this parallelism.

Defining the precise boundaries of a dataflow language poses a challenge due to its overlapping characteristics with other language classes. Dataflow programming languages are not exclusive to dataflow machines, and specific languages not designed initially for dataflow have been found effective in this context. Consequently, the distinction of what constitutes a dataflow language becomes somewhat blurred. However, there are essential core features that are commonly associated with dataflow languages identified by Ackerman [1], Whiting and Pascoe [84], Wail and Abramson [80]. These features include:

1. Freedom from side effects
2. Locality of effect
3. Data dependencies equivalent to scheduling
4. Single assignment of variables
5. Unusual notation for iterations due to features 1 and 4
6. Lack of history sensitivity in procedures

Since scheduling relies on data dependencies, it is crucial to ensure that variable values remain unchanged between their assignment and usage. To guarantee this, dataflow languages typically prohibit variable reassignment once a value has been assigned. This adherence to the single-assignment rule allows variables to be treated as values, imparting a robust functional programming flavor. Notably, the single-assignment rule enables the compiler to represent each value as one or more arcs in the resulting dataflow graph, connecting the instruction that assigns the value to subsequent instructions that rely on it.

6 Application domain

6.1 Dataflow in signal processing

Signal processing originated from circuit theory and is based on the idea of modeling algorithms as compositions of components that operate concurrently and communicate through signals. These signals represent functions of time and traditional signal processing deals with continuous-time signals. However, contemporary signal processing often involves discrete-time signals, where computation is regulated by a discrete clock rather than a continuous time continuum. Multiple clocks may be used in multi-rate systems, but there are clear relationships among them to ensure an unambiguous association of clock ticks. Synchronous languages and Dennis[19][18] and Kahn-style [30] dataflow models can be compared to synchronous and self-timed circuits. In the synchronous model, tokens (representing data) are globally ordered based on a global clock. In the Dennis and Kahn dataflow model, tokens are streams with relative ordering within a stream but no necessary ordering across streams. Data precedences in actors or processes impose partial ordering constraints on tokens across streams. Using streams of tokens as an abstraction for signals and dataflow actors or Kahn processes as an abstraction for components, the notion of time is lost, but data precedences are preserved. This abstraction allows for high concurrency since only data precedences need to be respected, eliminating the need for tight coordination based on a global time ordering. This reduction of stream-based processing to its computational essence is arguable and provides a highly concurrent approach to signal processing[59].

6.2 Dataflow for reconfigurable computing

The model of dataflow graph program representation has set the foundation for programming reconfigurable computing machines (RCMs). Reconfigurable computing [23] involves mapping and remapping computations directly onto hardware, and it has gained renewed attention with the advancement of FPGA devices [10] and VLSI technology. The reconfigurable computing model balances generality and efficiency, providing higher operation density than general-purpose processors and overcoming limitations of the von Neumann stored-program model. It combines aspects of SIMD, systolic arrays, and MIMD models, allowing for varying computation granularity from bit-level manipulations to high-level parallelism. However, programmability remains a significant challenge for the broader acceptance of RCMs, especially with the flexibility offered by dynamic reconfiguration [59].

A reconfigurable computing machine typically consists of a processor and an array of programmable blocks (RC array). The granularity of these programmable blocks can vary significantly. FPGA-based machines have fine-grained blocks composed of logic gates [54] [53] while coarse-grain

reconfigurable machines have blocks including an ALU and a register file. RCM architectures can be specialized processors, coprocessors, or attached processors, serving specific purposes such as neural network computations. Developing an accessible and efficient programming paradigm for reconfigurable computing is an important research focus in addressing the programmability challenges of RCMs.

6.3 Dataflow for Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning:

Artificial intelligence (AI) applications are expanding in various fields, including computer vision, robotics, and natural language understanding. As these AI applications become more complex, there is a growing need for reliable and high-performance computers that can efficiently execute AI algorithms. Conventional numerically oriented von Neumann computers may not be suitable for AI software, as AI has distinct computational requirements compared to numerical applications.

AI computations require symbolic processing, non-deterministic computations, knowledge representation and manipulation, parallel and distributed processing, and dynamic resource allocation. Many AI computations are data-dependent, meaning the execution path is determined at runtime based on the processed data, necessitating dynamic resource allocation. Traditional computer architectures address this requirement through special-purpose stacks, heaps, pointers, and dynamic garbage collection. However, an architecture based on the dataflow principle proposed by Dennis [17] could handle these runtime requirements with minimal overhead.

A multiprocessor dataflow architecture generates and manages tokens that can be executed independently, aligning well with the needs of AI applications. Jose [16] proposes a novel dataflow-based architecture called the SUNY dataflow machine, specifically designed to support artificial intelligence applications. The machine has been studied for programming applications in the AI domain.

Artificial neural networks are parallel interconnected networks composed of simple elements[44]. To achieve high performance in implementing neural networks, parallel hardware is required. There are two main approaches for hardware implementations: specialized machines and general-purpose parallel machines. Specialized machines tend to offer higher performance. Dataflow computers are a type of parallel system that differs from other architectures in that they lack an instruction pointer.

Thomas [69] has proposed a novel approach for artificial neural network computing using dataflow computers. This approach offers several advantages, including increased flexibility, more efficient implementations of sparsely connected neurons, and the ability to implement learning algorithms within the same machine.

When incorporating neuromorphic systems[58] [55] for conventional machine learning tasks, a challenge arises regarding the representation of numeric values inherent in machine learning data as spikes. Rate-based coding offers simplicity and effectiveness but lacks efficiency, while time-based coding is efficient in terms of power consumption but slower and computationally complex. Similar to the field of neuromorphic engineering, the growing prominence of machine learning has sparked a renewed interest in dataflow architectures. Consequently, several new companies are actively developing coarse- and fine-grained dataflow architectures specifically designed for AI applications [60]. NeuronFlow [58] is an innovative computing architecture that integrates neuromorphic computing and dataflow architecture. It addresses the inherent coding challenges associated with spiking systems and is well-suited for procedural workload and deep neural network (DNN) inference. This architecture is especially advantageous for performing computations on sparse convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and low-latency applications.

7 Challenges and solutions

Dataflow architecture is a computing paradigm that focuses on the flow of data between tasks or operations rather than control flow. While dataflow architectures offer advantages such as efficient parallelism and scalable execution, they also present specific challenges that must be addressed for optimal performance. Here is an elaboration of the challenges and solutions in dataflow architecture: **Challenges:**

- **Data Dependency:** Data dependencies occur when the output of one task depends on the input of another task. Managing these dependencies in a dataflow graph can be complex, particularly in large-scale applications. To ensure correct execution order and avoid data hazards, data dependencies must be accurately tracked.
- **Task Scheduling:** Determining the optimal scheduling of tasks in a dataflow graph is challenging, especially in dynamic and unpredictable environments. Efficient task scheduling is crucial to maximize resource utilization and minimize latency. However, scheduling decisions must consider data dependencies, resource availability, and task priorities.
- **Memory Management:** In dataflow architectures, managing data storage and memory allocation can be challenging, especially for large and complex applications. Efficient memory management techniques are required to minimize data movement and optimize memory usage. Excessive data transfers and storage overhead can significantly impact performance without proper memory management.
- **Load Balancing:** Load balancing involves distributing the workload evenly among different processing elements or nodes in a dataflow system. It is essential

to achieve efficient parallelism and prevent underutilization of resources. Load imbalances can lead to performance degradation and decreased overall system efficiency.

Solutions:

- **Dataflow Analysis:** Advanced dataflow analysis techniques, such as static analysis and dataflow profiling, can help identify and optimize data dependencies in a graph. These techniques aid in efficient task scheduling and resource allocation by providing insights into data flow patterns and dependencies.
- **Task Scheduling Algorithms:** Various scheduling algorithms can be employed to optimize task execution in a dataflow architecture. Examples include list scheduling, dynamic scheduling, and critical path scheduling. These algorithms consider factors such as data dependencies, resource availability, and task priorities to determine the optimal execution order of tasks.
- **Memory Hierarchy Design:** Incorporating memory hierarchies and caching mechanisms in dataflow architectures helps reduce data movement and improve memory access latency. Techniques like data prefetching (anticipating data needs) and memory reuse (minimizing redundant data transfers) enhance memory management efficiency, improving overall system performance.
- **Dynamic Load Balancing:** Dynamic load balancing algorithms continuously monitor the workload distribution in a dataflow system and redistribute tasks among processing elements to achieve load balance. Load balancing techniques, such as work stealing (moving tasks from busy processors to idle ones) and task migration (moving tasks to balance the load), help optimize resource utilization and improve system performance.
- **Compilation Techniques:** Advanced compiler optimizations specifically designed for dataflow architectures can analyze and transform the dataflow graph to optimize resource utilization, reduce data dependencies, and enhance overall system performance. These optimizations may include loop unrolling, code motion, and register allocation techniques tailored to dataflow execution.
- **Hardware Support:** Specialized hardware accelerators and architectures tailored for execution can efficiently support dataflow-based applications. These hardware solutions can include specialized memory structures, parallel processing units, and optimized interconnects to handle the unique requirements of dataflow architectures. Hardware support can significantly improve performance and scalability in dataflow systems.

By addressing these challenges and implementing suitable solutions, dataflow architectures can overcome their inherent

complexities and deliver efficient execution, parallelism, and performance for various applications.

8 Summary

In conclusion, this report has examined the salient differences among various dataflow architectures and their implementations. It has highlighted vital aspects such as design approaches, execution models, programmability, and application domains. By understanding these differences, researchers and practitioners can make informed decisions when selecting and designing dataflow architectures for specific use cases.

Furthermore, the report acknowledges that different dataflow architectures bring their unique challenges. These challenges include managing data dependencies, handling dynamic data streams, optimizing performance and energy efficiency, enabling hardware-software co-design, managing runtime reconfigurability, and addressing programmability issues. The report suggests that novel design techniques, runtime management approaches, and hardware optimizations should be explored and implemented to overcome these challenges.

By advancing the understanding of dataflow architectures and addressing their challenges, researchers and engineers can unlock their full potential in embedded systems, multimedia processing, machine learning, cryptography, cloud computing, and edge computing.

Overall this report is a valuable resource for those interested in dataflow architectures, providing insights into their differences, implementation considerations, and potential solutions to overcome challenges. It encourages further exploration and innovation in dataflow architectures to drive advancements in computing systems and their applications.

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